

THE FIRST CLINICAL RESULTS OF A NEW METHOD FOR PROVIDING AERO- AND HEMOSTASIS IN LUNG SURGERY

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Abstract. For clinical surgery, a method for preventing the development of disorders of aero- and hemostasis has been improved, providing for two-component strengthening of the zone of resected lung tissue by local application of a hemostatic agent with the formation of an airtight film followed by fixation of the parietal pleural leaf to it. Clinical studies were conducted among patients operated on from 2019 to May 2023, the material was accumulated at the Khorezm Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. After performing the main stage of marginal lung resection intraoperatively, when checking for tightness, only 38.5% of cases showed high-quality aero- and hemostasis, in turn, 61.5% showed inconsistency in these factors, including 24.6% - inadequate hemostasis, 18.0% - inadequate aerostasis and 18.9% have a combination of these complications. The conducted studies have allowed us to substantiate that the proposed method of providing hemo- and aerostasis in lung surgery has obvious advantages, significantly reducing the risk of developing these complications.

Key words: aerostasis failure; alveolar-pleural fistulas; postoperative complications; Hemoben.

For clinical surgery, a method for preventing the development of disorders of aero- and hemostasis has been improved, providing for two-component strengthening of the zone of resected lung tissue by local application of a hemostatic agent with the formation of an airtight film followed by fixation of the parietal pleural leaf to it [1-5].

Materials and methods. Clinical studies were conducted among patients operated on from 2019 to May 2023, the material was accumulated at the Khorezm Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. There were a total of 122 patients with various benign lung diseases who underwent resection interventions. In the main group of 58 patients (2022-2023), after the resection stage of lung surgery, the proposed method was applied using the domestic hemostatic agent Hemoben to achieve stable aero- and hemostasis. The comparison group included 64 patients (2019-2021) who were comparable in gender, age, pathology and other objective criteria, and aero- and hemostasis was achieved by traditional surgical options.

Results. After performing the main stage of marginal lung resection intraoperatively, when checking for tightness, only 38.5% (in both groups, 47 out of 122 patients) of cases showed high-quality aero- and hemostasis, in turn, 61.5% (in both groups, 75 out of 122 patients) showed inconsistency in these factors, including 24.6% (30 patients) - inadequate hemostasis, 18.0% (22 patients) - inadequate aerostasis and 18.9% (23 patients) have a combination of these complications. The introduction of a new method of local application of hemostatic Hemoben after performing the main stage of lung resection allowed to increase the effectiveness of aero- and hemostasis from 40.6% (in 25 out of 64 patients in the comparison group) to 87.9% (in 51 out of 58 patients in the main group), which in turn reduced the need for additional stitching lung tissue from 59.4% (in 38 patients in the comparison group) to 12.1% (in 7 of 58 patients in the main group; $\chi^2=31.022$; $df=2$; $p<0.001$), while repeated application of a hemostatic agent with fixation on top of the resected surface of the lung leaf of the parietal pleura intraoperatively ensured 100% quality of achieved aero- and hemostasis.

Even under the condition of verified intraoperatively adequate aero- and hemostasis, in the early postoperative period, in 7.7% of cases in the control group (out of 26 patients, 1 had a hemostasis disorder and a combination of aero- and hemostasis disorders in another 1 patient), the development of these complications was noted, while in the main group, the use of the new method allowed in 100% cases to achieve the absence of this risk ($\chi^2=1.687$; $df=1$; $p=0.194$). In turn, among patients with intraoperative use of additional stitching of lung tissue in the early period after surgery, the use of a new method of strengthening the resected surface of lung tissue allowed to reduce the incidence of aero- and hemostasis disorders from 18.4% (in 7 (3 - hemostasis; 3 - aerostasis; 1 - combination of aero- and hemostasis disorders) from 38 patients in the comparison group) up to 2.7% (in 1 (hemostasis) of 37 patients in the main group; $\chi^2=4,861$; $df=1$; $p=0.028$).

In general, the use of a new method of hemo- and aerostasis in lung surgery provided a significant reduction in the risk of developing these complications in the early postoperative period. In general, the incidence of complications decreased from 15.6% (in 10 out of 64 patients in the comparison group) to 3.4% (in 2 out of 58 patients in the main group; $\chi^2=5.087$; $df=1$; $p=0.025$), among which the impairment of aero- and hemostasis decreased from 14.1% (in 9 patients in the comparison group) up to 1.7% (1 patient in the main group), respectively, this reduced the need for conservative resolution of complications

from 9.4% (in 6 patients in the comparison group) to 1.7% (in 1 in the main group), as well as completely offset the risk of repeated interventions (4.7% in the group comparison; $\chi^2=6,327$; $df=1$; $p=0.043$). Reducing the risk of postoperative complications made it possible to reduce the duration of drainage from 3.9 ± 2.5 days in the comparison group to 2.9 ± 1.2 days in the main group ($t=2.79$; $p<0.05$), as well as the duration of postoperative hospital rehabilitation from 7.7 ± 2.7 to 6.3 ± 1.6 days ($t=3.53$; $p<0.05$).

Conclusion. The conducted studies have allowed us to substantiate that the proposed method of providing hemo- and aerostasis in lung surgery has obvious advantages, significantly reducing the risk of developing these complications

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